

ONLINE PROCESS MONITORING IN HYBRID INJECTION OVERMOULDING

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Motivation

- Hybrid injection overmoulding combines properties of organosheets and injection moulding:
 - Excellent mechanical properties
 - High degrees of geometric freedom and short cycle times
- Strength of hybrid structures is primarily determined by the interface between insert and injection moulding compound
- Use for safety-critical parts (e.g. aerospace primary structures) is hindered by incomplete understanding of the process and lack of quality assurance

Goals

- Tool development for fabrication of specimen and online process monitoring
- Measuring of decisive process variables inside the mould cavity via integrated sensors
- Evaluation of tool and sensor system through a statistical test plan
- Study effects of various machine and process parameters on measured in-cavity process variables and bonding properties
- Definition of a process window for the complete bond formation between insert and injection moulding compound as a basis for quality assurance

Overmoulding Tool & Test Specimen

- Test specimen for the determination of bonding properties at the interface
- Organosheet insert overmoulded with short-fibre reinforced thermoplastic ribs
- Double rip geometry to prevent bending of organosheet in tensile test
- Variable tool design allows variable insert thickness, injection sequence, distance from gate and creation of weld lines
- Wide range of processible materials up to high temperature thermoplastics such as PEEK

Sensor System

- Three different types and a total of eight sensors included in the tool
- Measurement of insert, mould and melt temperatures throughout the injection process
- Placement of sensors allows determination of melt flow rate in the cavity
- All sensors were provided by project partner FOS Messtechnik GmbH within the scope of the research project QuaSimOdo (Quality assurance in the overmoulding process – online)

Experimental Procedure

- Statistical test plan (DoE 2⁵-plan with centre point; 170 parts, 850 tensile specimen) to determine effects of process and machine parameters
- Material system
 - Insert: PP-GF organosheet; 2.5 mm; Bondlaminates Tepex® dynalite
 - Injection moulding compound: PP-GF, short fibre reinforced; Borealis GB205U
- Effects on in-cavity temperature, flow rate and bonding strength investigated
- Investigated process parameters:
 - Melt temperature
 - Tool temperature
 - Oven temperature
 - Injection speed
 - Holding pressure

Process parameters	Lower level	Centre point	Upper level
Melt temp. [°C]	200	240	280
Tool temp. [°C]	20	40	60
Oven temp. [°C]	50	100	150
Injection speed. [%]	-50 %	Standard	50 %
Holding pressure [bar]	200	300	400

Statistical test plan (DoE 2⁵-plan with centre point)

Results

- Statistically significant effects investigated:
 - for in-cavity temperature: Melt temperature
 - for flow rate: Injection speed, melt temperature
 - for interface bond strength: Oven temperature, melt temperature, injection speed, tool temperature
- The bond strength as a main quality criteria is most heavily influenced by melt and oven temperature, resulting in a higher interface temperature

Conclusion

- The developed test specimen is capable of indicating the effects of various process parameters on interface bond strength
- The integrated sensor system measures in-cavity temperatures of melt, insert and mould online and throughout the injection process
- Melt temperature and preheating of the insert have been identified as the most influential factors for high interface strength

- The developed process monitoring system will be transferred to high temperature thermoplastic materials within the scope of the HiQO (High Quality Overmoulding) research project
- For process validation a generic aerospace component will be manufactured
- Online measured process variables and quality assessment are stored in a electronic component file

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